

Relevance of civil law regulation insurance of foreign investments in Uzbekistan

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***Abstract** : this article examines the features of civil regulation of foreign investment insurance in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the process of formation of investment legislation of Uzbekistan, the role of the state in the process of legal regulation of investment activities in the Republic of Uzbekistan, attention is paid to the features of the legal status of foreign investments. The article provides definitions of the main concepts in the field of investment insurance. A comparative analysis of the civil legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in force in the field of regulation of foreign investment insurance and the investment legislation of the Russian Federation is carried out. Also, the views of legal scholars on the problems of legal regulation in the field of investment activities are given.*

***Key words:** investments, foreign investments, civil legislation, investment legislation, civil law regulation, investment activity, foreign investors.*

In recent years, fundamental economic transformations have been taking place in Uzbekistan, characterized by active growth of international economic cooperation and ever-increasing attraction of foreign investments. In these conditions, issues of insurance of investment activities of foreign entities are becoming increasingly important.

The active integration processes between states in the sphere of foreign investment determine the close interaction of national and international law. [1] The mutual influence of these two independent legal systems also covers the sphere of insurance of foreign investments. According to experts, there is legal regulation of foreign investments at two levels: national- legal and international-legal levels. Speaking about the regulation of relations in the sphere of foreign investments at the national-legal level, legal scholars

emphasize that general regulation in the field of foreign investments is ensured by national legislation (investment, civil, trade, etc.). [2]

In this case, legal regulation in the field of foreign investment insurance at the national level is carried out mainly in the civil legislation segment. Civil-legal regulation of relations in the area under consideration in each country has its own specifics. The specifics of civil-legal regulation of relations in the field of investment insurance in Uzbekistan are determined by the organizational and legal foundations, forms and methods of implementing insurance in this area. At present, in Uzbekistan, the priority in creating the organizational and legal foundations of insurance and investment activities belongs to the state. The regulatory role of the state in the process of investment insurance is manifested in the adoption of legislative and by-laws regulating legal relations in this area, in the supervision of the activities of entities engaged in insurance activities, as well as in the implementation of a unified tax policy. [3]

It is important that in the years since the Republic of Uzbekistan gained state independence, civil legislation has been formed in the country, ensuring guarantees of the rights of foreign investors. Today, civil-legal regulation of relations in the sphere of investment insurance is carried out on the basis of such legislative acts as: the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Insurance Activities ", the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Investments and Investment Activities", etc.

At the same time, legal scholars note the following: despite the fact that legal guarantees for foreign investment are enshrined in law, the recipient state in practice cannot always ensure precise and strict compliance with these guarantees due to the political instability inherent in developing countries and countries with so-called transition economies.[4] Therefore, in order to correctly understand the problems existing in the field of ensuring the rights of foreign investors, it is first necessary to determine what the

specifics of the legal protection of foreign investment are. In this regard, it should be noted that the very concept of foreign investment differs both in scientific literature and in legislation from the concept of investment in general. From the point of view of specialists in the field of investment law, and foreign investment is the investment of foreign capital in an object of entrepreneurial activity on the territory of a state in the form of objects of civil rights belonging to a foreign investor, if such objects of civil rights are not withdrawn from circulation or are not restricted in circulation in accordance with the laws of the country receiving the investment, including money, securities, other property, property rights that have a monetary value, exclusive rights to the results of intellectual activity (intellectual property), as well as services and information.[5]

The concept of foreign investment is also reflected in the national legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. According to its norms, foreign investment is tangible and intangible assets and rights to them, including rights to intellectual property, as well as reinvestments made by a foreign investor in social sphere objects, entrepreneurial, scientific and other types of activities (Article 3 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Investments and Investment Activities"). This definition is quite brief. For comparison, the legislation of the Russian Federation defines foreign investment as an investment of foreign capital, carried out by a foreign investor directly and independently, in an object of entrepreneurial activity on the territory of the Russian Federation in the form of objects of civil rights belonging to a foreign investor, if such objects of civil rights are not withdrawn from circulation or are not restricted in circulation in the Russian Federation in accordance with federal [laws](#), including money, securities (in foreign currency and the currency of the Russian Federation), other property, property rights that have a monetary value, exclusive rights to the results of intellectual activity (intellectual property), as well as services and information (Article 2 of the Law of the Russian Federation "On Foreign Investments in the Russian Federation").

The specificity of legal protection of foreign investments is manifested in the fact that

foreign investors, as a rule, are provided with additional legal guarantees. The state guarantees the protection of the rights and legitimate interests of foreign investors on the basis of generally recognized international legal standards, with which domestic legislation is harmonized. In this regard, the national legislation of Uzbekistan is no exception.

Currently, the civil legislation of Uzbekistan provides a number of additional legal guarantees to foreign investors. In particular, guarantees for the return of foreign investments in connection with the termination of investment activities, as well as a guarantee against unfavorable changes in legislation are provided (Articles 18 and 19 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Investments and Investment Activities"). It is also important for foreign investors that the state guarantees the protection of investments in accordance with the legislation and international treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Article 21 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Investments and Investment Activities"). In this aspect, it is necessary to emphasize that the civil legislation provides for almost all the basic guarantees of the rights and legitimate interests of foreign investors.

At the same time, an analysis of the investment legislation of Uzbekistan showed that it does not contain special provisions devoted to the insurance of investment activities. It is believed that this is a shortcoming of the current investment legislation, since, from the point of view of legal scholars, foreign investors are trying to create a system of additional guarantees that protect investors from non-commercial risks. One of the elements of such a system of additional guarantees is a system of insurance of non-commercial risks.

The experience of foreign lawmaking also shows that investment legislation contains legal norms regulating investment insurance issues. In particular, the Law of the Russian Federation "On Foreign Investments in the Russian Federation" contains a separate article 18 regulating property insurance carried out by a commercial organization with foreign investments and a branch, representative office of a foreign legal entity.

In addition, the civil-law features of insurance in this area are due to the fact that the

object of insurance is investment activity. Investment activity is mediated by investment relations arising on the basis of agreements between participants in investment activity and being the subject of civil-law regulation. Public organization of investment activity is implemented within the framework of public relations, which are the subject of public regulation (legislative, administrative , procedural). The nature of investment (private) relations is determined by the nature of investment activity based on the investor's own interest, freedom of his will, as well as the nature of the activities of public authorities establishing and controlling the limits of freedom of investment activity. [6] The civil legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan defines investment activity as a set of actions of subjects of investment activity related to the implementation of investments (Article 3 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Investments and Investment Activity").

In the area of legal relations under study, it should be noted that scientists involved in issues of international legal protection of foreign investments note that in the course of many years of international practice, various forms and methods of preventing or at least reducing risks have been developed. From a legal point of view, the mechanisms for preventing or reducing commercial and non-commercial risks are completely different, since by their nature, by their character and subjects in the relevant relations, each of these methods has a special meaning and content. But, nevertheless, the ultimate goal of applying the forms and methods of eliminating risks coincides: to prevent risks for foreign investments. [7]

Currently, based on the industry criterion, which takes into account the subject composition, source of capital and legal consequences of the occurrence of insured events, as a result of which the investor's rights are transferred to specialized state or international agencies, experts distinguish two types of legal insurance mechanisms.

- international legal mechanism - investment insurance carried out by international intergovernmental organizations, as well as the provision of guarantees within the framework of national investment insurance systems abroad on the basis of bilateral

agreements,

- private law mechanism - insurance carried out by private insurance companies. [7]

An analysis of specialized literature and foreign legislation shows the importance of legislative consolidation of additional guarantees for the implementation of foreign investments. However, according to some experts, the problem of proper legal regulation of activities involving foreign investors is not limited to creating a favorable regime for foreign investments and securing guarantees for their implementation, but is also aimed at ensuring and protecting public interests. Therefore, the state can establish certain restrictions when implementing foreign investments.[1]

Thus, based on a comprehensive analysis of the civil legislation of Uzbekistan and scientific literature on this topic, a conclusion was made on the need to supplement the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Investments and Investment Activities" with separate articles that would establish insurance of investment activities as one of the additional guarantees of the rights of foreign investors, as well as regulating the types of investment insurance.

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